

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

INTERPRETATION AND RESEARCHES

 ISSN: 2181-4163

 IMPACT FACTOR: 8.2

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The international scientific journal "Interpretation and researches" publishes the results of scientific research conducted by school teachers, university students, professors and teachers, and independent researchers in the form of scientific articles. This journal is indexed in authoritative databases and published in electronic form.

The international scientific journal has certificate No. 054841 of the Agency for the Development of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The journal accepts articles in the following areas: 1. Exact sciences 2. Natural sciences 3. Engineering sciences 4. Pedagogical sciences 5. Social and human sciences 6. Medical sciences. Note for authors of articles: articles are accepted in Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak.

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11(83)

30.05.2026

International scientific journal
“INTERPRETATION AND RESEARCHES”

volume 1 issue 11(83)
30. 05. 2026

interpretationandresearches.uz

International scientific
journal
“Interpretation and
researches”

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Jurnal O'zbekiston
Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligi
tomonidan
2022- yil 22-dekabr sanasida
№054841 raqam bilan davlat
ro'yxatidan o'tkazilgan

ISSN 2181 - 4163

Jurnaldan maqola ko'chirib
bosilganda, manba
ko'rsatilishi shart.

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CORRECTIONAL WORK SYSTEM AND LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF GRAPHOMOTOR SKILLS IN MENTALLY RETARDED CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations of the formation of graphomotor skills in mentally retarded children, the system of correctional work, and the importance of modern learning technologies. It analyzes that the level of development of graphomotor skills is closely related to the child's writing activity, fine motor skills, visual-motor coordination, and general mental development. It also describes a staged correctional work model aimed at developing graphomotor skills, a system of effective exercises, and pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: graphomotor skills, fine motor skills, visual-motor coordination, correctional work, mentally retarded children, speech therapy technologies.

Writing activity in the educational process is an important component of the child's cognitive, motor and psychological development. In particular, the process of preparing for writing in mentally retarded children requires a special approach. In this category of children, graphomotor skills are not sufficiently developed, which leads to difficulties in the processes of writing, drawing, perception and re-expression of signs.

Graphomotor skills are the integration of movement, coordination, and cognitive processes necessary for writing and visual activities. These skills are not only related to writing techniques, but also to psychomotor development.

Graphomotor skills are an interconnected system of visual perception, fine motor skills, and coordination of movements. Scientific research shows that writing activity is based on the following components: visual-motor coordination; fine motor development; spatial perception; movement planning (praxis); attention and memory processes. In children with mental retardation, various degrees of deficits are observed in the development of these functions.

The process of forming graphomotor skills should be organized on the basis of an integrated approach. Correctional work covers the following areas. Fine motor skills are the basis of graphomotor activity. finger gymnastics; working with plasticine; mosaic typing; buttoning; cutting and gluing.

The acquisition of graphomotor skills plays a major role in eliminating writing deficiencies. Writing is a complex skill that requires coordinated movements of the muscles of the palm and hand. Mastering writing skills is a continuous process that requires overcoming great difficulties, and not all children can master it immediately. Writing is a form of speech in which it is recorded on paper by recording graphic signs corresponding to the elements of oral speech. Writing in the Uzbek language is based on sound-letter signs. The formation of graphic writing skills is considered the main unit in education.

Before explaining the concept of graphomotor skills, first of all, we need to understand what a skill is. A skill is an action that, through constant repetition, becomes automatic. A distinctive feature of performing such an action is that it does not require constant attention and control. Many automated actions or skills arise in connection with the implementation of a certain type of activity (educational, everyday, professional skills). In addition, we can divide skills into mnemonic (related to memorization and reproduction), speech, mental, motor, and graphomotor skills.

In the formation of skills, cognitive (related to cognitive processes) and sensory-motor components, control of the performed movement, spatial orientation, etc. play an important role. The ability to form and reproduce skills is one of the most important indicators of general intellectual potential.

Graphomotor skills are the specific position and movement of the leading hand that allows you to draw simple patterns, connect dots and lines, and color pictures. The tasks of graphomotor skills include:

- visual perception of the given material;
- attention;
- correct holding of a pencil or pen;
- appropriate pressure of the pencil when writing;
- rhythm of movements;
- accuracy in tracing lines.

It is important to develop graphomotor skills in children from an early age. If the formation of graphomotor skills begins at an early age, then in most cases these children will not have any problems in mastering the school curriculum. At each age, there is a specific level of development of graphomotor skills. In this regard, it is possible to determine whether a child corresponds to a certain level of development or lags behind. According to M. M. Bezrukikh[14]: “Graphic skills imply a certain habitual position and movements of the writing hand, which allow depicting and connecting letter symbols. If graphomotor skills are fully formed, the child writes letters clearly, beautifully and quickly, if graphomotor skills are not formed, certain

difficulties may arise in writing: incomprehensible and ugly handwriting, a slowdown in the writing process, among others”.

The underdevelopment of graphomotor skills manifests itself in everyday activities, and it is very easy for parents or teachers to notice this.

A child with underdeveloped graphomotor skills:

- does not strive for handicraft activities;
- refuses to draw;
- has difficulty taking care of himself (dressing, tying shoelaces);
- his drawings are not the same as those of his peers, he holds a pencil incorrectly.

Many children have difficulty with actions that require precision and synchronization of movements. Cutting something, sculpting, drawing a contour, using plasticine - all this does not cause problems for adults, but for preschool children it is a simple difficulties with visible movements occur. If a child has poorly developed graphomotor skills, he will have problems with writing during school and his academic performance will decrease. Therefore, efforts should be made to develop graphomotor skills in children from an early age.

The process of forming the basis of graphomotor skills is directly related to the development of such components as general and fine motor skills, phonemic perception and auditory analysis, visual-spatial imagination, visual-motor coordination, and the level of speech development. Therefore, the process of preparing a child for school should include the formation of fine and general motor skills, attention and visual imagination. When teaching the initial skills of writing, it is necessary to take into account not only the level of general and speech development of the child, but also the level of development of psychophysical functions (phonemic perception, correct pronunciation of sounds, spatial orientation, level of development of attention and memory). The effectiveness of teaching a preschool child writing skills partly depends on the level of formation of fine motor skills of the fingers and general motor skills of the working hand. The palmar projection accounts for approximately 1/3 of the motor projection area in the cerebral cortex. It is located next to the speech motor area, which explains in detail why working on the fine motor skills of the fingers has a strong impact on the level of speech development.

According to M. M. Koltsova[44] and a number of other researchers, there are sufficient grounds to consider the palm of the hand as a full-fledged speech organ, just like the articulatory apparatus. From this point of view, the projection of the hand in the brain can be considered another speech area. Studies have shown that if the level of development of the fingers of the hand corresponds to the age norm, the level of speech development is also normal, and vice versa, if the development of finger

movements lags behind, speech development also lags behind, but in this case, general motor skills may represent normal indicators, or even be very well developed.

The formation of graphomotor skills in mentally retarded children is a long-term, systematic and complex process that requires an integrated approach. In this process, the development of fine motor skills, visual-motor coordination, spatial perception and accuracy of movement is of great importance. The use of modern pedagogical technologies significantly increases the effectiveness of correctional work.

Graphomotor exercises not only develop writing skills, but also have a positive effect on the general mental development of the child.

References:

1. Amirsaidova Sh.M. The place and role of the ideas of the Eastern thinker in the development of special pedagogy. Ped.fan.nomz. diss. autoref. – T.: 2006. – 37 p.;
2. D.A. Nurkeldiyeva, Z.I. Islambekova "Diagnosis of children with developmental disabilities", T-2013
3. Vygotsky, L. S. (1993). Psychology and special pedagogy. Moscow: Prosveshcheniye
4. Akramova Kh.S. Technology of using a computer program in the formation of labor skills in mentally retarded students of grades 4-5: dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogy. Abstract. –T., 2023. -49 p.
5. Muminova L.R. Teoreticheskie osnovy korektsionno pedagogicheskoy raboty po preodoleniyu chevogo nedorazvitiya u detey doshkolnogo vozrasta: Autoref. diss... doc. ped. science - T.: TGPU, 1992. - 46 p.
6. Akramova H.S. The technology of using a computer program in the formation of work skills in 4th-5th grade students with mental retardation: Autoref. diss. ped. science. doc (PhD)... - T.: TDPU, 2020. —24 p.

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International scientific journal
“Interpretation and researches”
xalqaro ilmiy jurnal
2026-yil 11(83)-son

© Mualliflar jamoasi, 30.05.2026. 158 bet.

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